

VARIATIONS ON ITAKURA'S SPECTRAL MATCH SCORE

Dean P. McCullough

Department of Defense
Fort George G. Meade, Maryland 20755

ABSTRACT

F. Itakura's spectral match score is commonly used in the automatic recognition of continuous speech to compare a template to the continuous speech. This paper demonstrates that a symmetric version of this score adds some strength to the original score. It also demonstrates that by oversampling a band-limited signal, energy information is incorporated into this spectral match score, the energy level of a frame being contained in the in-band to out-of-band energy level ratio. This energy information further improves the automatic recognition process. A technique is presented which makes effective use of this energy information, without changing the sampling rate.

INTRODUCTION

One important problem in the automatic recognition of speech is the determination of the degree of similarity between a template frame and a speech frame. In [1], F. Itakura developed a linear prediction coefficient (LPC) based spectral match score to do this. Itakura's score was originally used to identify which of several templates best fit an isolated utterance i.e., the isolated word problem. In several systems, however, variations of this score have been used with continuous speech. See [2] and [3] for examples.

The problem studied in this report is the location and identification of target words in continuous speech, i.e., the wordspotting problem. The goal of the experiments described here is to examine the effects of variations of Itakura's spectral match score on the recognition rate of a set of ten target words, to develop variations of this score with improved recognition rates, and to provide guidelines for the selection of optimal parameter values.

DATA BASE

The data base used in these experiments consists of 17.5 minutes of material extracted from conversational style speech spoken by eight talkers (6 males and 2 females). The speech was collected from a contrived two-way telephone conversation, in which the conversants were

cooperatively planning a road rally course. This speech was recorded under laboratory conditions, digitized at 10 KHz, and was subsequently digitally filtered to a band of approximately 350 Hz to 3350 Hz to simulate a telephone band. This resulted in a -40 dB average in-band signal to out-of-band noise floor ratio. The ten target words were selected, and appear in Table 1 along with the number of occurrences of each. Of the 150 occurrences of these ten target words in the data base, 63 were spoken by the two female talkers and 87 by the six male talkers.

Table 1: Target Words in Data Base

Boonsboro	25	Conway	15	Interstate	14
Look	4	Middleton	25	Mountain	25
Primary	17	Secondary	6	Sheffield	7
Westchester	12				

Four male talkers, distinct from those used in the conversational portion of this data base, were used to generate templates of these ten target words. One template of each target word was selected for these experiments. The template talkers also recorded a read passage which was used to generate the average spectrum for each template talker.

WORD RECOGNITION SYSTEM

The major components of the target word recognition system used in these experiments are shown in Figure 1. The average spectrum from the template talker and one generated from 30 seconds of speech for a target conversational speaker are used to generate a blind deconvolution filter [4] which is used to modify the template. Though intended as a channel normalization technique, this procedure has been found to provide some speaker normalization. Autocorrelation and LPC features using 12 poles are extracted every 10 ms using a 20 ms Hamming window. Variations of F. Itakura's spectral match score [1] are used to compare every frame of the speech to every frame of the template, and a dynamic program with step constraints similar to the Sakoe and Chiba constraints with $p=1$ [5] is used for time warping to obtain good scoring regions called putative hits. These putative hit scores are linearly scaled, independently for each speaker, to provide additional speaker normalization.

In order to evaluate the performance of an experiment, the number of target words scoring better than the *i*th false alarm is calculated for each template. From these, the overall percentage of target words recognized is calculated. The same false alarm level is used in all experiments in this report. It was set to provide an overall recognition rate of 40% of the target words in the experiment using Itakura's original score (defined by equation (1) below). The results of the various experiments are in Table 2, at the end of this report.

SYMMETRIC ITAKURA SCORE

F. Itakura's spectral match score (1) can be defined as:

$$D(S,T) = \text{Ln} \left(\frac{a_t R_s a'_t}{a_s R_t a'_s} \right) \quad (1)$$

where a_x is the vector of LPC coefficients for a speech ($x=s$) or template ($x=t$) frame, and R_x is the autocorrelation matrix. C. A. Olano and R. E. Wohlford first noted in 1976 that there existed speech frames which matched well with all of the template frames. This appears to result when the speech frame is primarily noise like, in which case the prediction residual, $a_s R_s a'_s$, is quite large.

The problem which Itakura was attempting to solve was to identify which of several models best fit an isolated utterance. In this case, the tendency for a speech frame to match all template frames well would appear to bias all templates approximately equally, and thus not seriously affect the results. However, the problem under study here is to find the locations in continuous speech which fit sufficiently well with a single model. Thus, the presence of speech frames with biased match scores would bias the resulting likelihood of the target word at those positions.

After looking at several other possibilities Olano suggested in the spring of 1976 a symmetric version of this spectral match score. This score

can be defined as:

$$D'(S,T) = \text{Ln} \left(\frac{a_t R_s a'_t}{a_s R_s a'_s} \quad \frac{a_s R_t a'_s}{a_t R_t a'_t} \right) \quad (2)$$

This formulation reflects the philosophy that in the problem being studied here, the match score used should be a metric, i.e., should be reflexive. This variation of Itakura's score is fairly obvious, and has probably been independently developed many times elsewhere. It appears in [6], for example.

Using equation (2) for the spectral match score resulted in a 46% recognition rate, significantly larger than the 40% obtained with (1). The symmetric version of Itakura's spectral match score (2) is used in all subsequent experiments described here.

SELECTIVE LPC

It had long been recognized that several problems existed with oversampling the signal, other than increased computational load. Because of the blind deconvolution filter, a faulty read of a single sample value would cause a mismatch in the out-of-band noise floor, and thus greatly reduce the recovery rate. Experiments in which Gaussian noise was added to the speech signal also had greatly reduced recognition rates for the same reason.

The selective LPC procedure [7] provides a technique for computing directly the autocorrelation coefficients resulting from filtering, translating to baseband, and down sampling the signal. (This technique consists of computing the autocorrelation coefficients from the modified Fourier coefficient magnitudes.) These autocorrelation coefficients can then be used to compute the LPC coefficients and an Itakura style match score exactly as before. Figure 2 displays the spectrum from a typical voiced frame, the corresponding full band LPC spectrum, and the selective LPC spectrum for the 350 to 3350 Hz band. The LPC spectrum resulting from this procedure appears to match the original

FIGURE 1: WORD RECOGNITION SYSTEM FOR CONTINUOUS SPEECH

signal in-band much better than does the full band LPC spectrum. This improved in-band match can be partly explained by the need for the full band LPC procedure to model the relatively sharp skirts of the band edge, resulting in distorted and exaggerated peaks near each band edge of the LPC spectrum.

Figure 2: Comparison of Selective LPC Spectrum, LPC Spectrum, and the Spectrum of the Original Signal

When this selective LPC procedure was tested using a band of 350 to 3350 Hz, only a 29% recognition rate was obtained. As the selective LPC bandwidth was allowed to approach the full band, the recovery rate approached that for the full band LPC.

It had always been thought that these Itakura type scores made no use of information on the relative energy in the template frame and speech frame. The LPC coefficients are unchanged by changes in the energy level, and the energy term in the autocorrelation matrix (the r_0 autocorrelation term) can be factored and cancels between the numerator and denominator in the equations above. However, in order to explain the very poor recovery rate with the selective LPC procedure, C. A. Olano hypothesized that energy information is retained in the autocorrelation coefficients (even after this cancellation) in the in-band to out-of-band energy level ratio. In order to test this hypothesis, the magnitudes of the out-of-band Fourier coefficients for each frame were replaced by the average of the coefficients in the 4000 to 5000 Hz range, and the autocorrelation coefficients were computed for the resulting spectrum. That is, the noise floor was smoothed to remove any spectral shape information. This resulted in a 45% recognition rate. Thus this hypothesis appears to explain the loss of performance by the selective LPC technique.

Since the procedure described above could be used to set as many out-of-band coefficients as desired, the effects of changing the sampling rate to vary the ratio of in-band to out-of-band

spectrum could easily be studied without actually resampling. Changing the sampling rate has the effect of varying the relative strengths of the in-band spectral match and relative energy components to the score. When coefficients for frequencies to 6000 Hz were set, the recognition rate fell slightly to 44%. Thus an in-band to out-of-band bandwidth ratio of approximately 2:1 appears reasonable. Several other experiments were tried, in which linear combinations of various forms of an energy ratio score and the spectral match score using selective LPC were used. However, no technique was found whose recognition rate approached the 46% found with the symmetric Itakura score.

AVERAGE LPC

The technique used in the above experiment has been extended to a technique which is independent of the actual out-of-band signal and sampling rate. The average in-band energy for each signal is computed, and a noise floor value of N dB down from this value is derived. The array of Fourier coefficient magnitudes squared is computed for each analysis frame. These are modified by setting all out-of-band coefficients to the derived noise floor value squared. The length of this array is modified to represent the desired new sampling rate. A cosine transform can then be used to compute each desired autocorrelation coefficient. The LPC coefficients and symmetric Itakura score can be computed in the usual way. In addition, the blind deconvolution filter algorithm was modified to use only the spectral ratios from the in-band portions of the spectrums. The out-of-band spectral ratios were set to the ratio at the nearest band edge.

This technique was tested with a -50 dB noise floor, and a 43% recognition rate was obtained. In order to verify that this process was properly eliminating the out-of-band signal, unfiltered, full band templates were used with the telephone bandwidth speech. In this test, a 45% recognition rate was achieved. Noise floors from -20 dB to -50 dB were tried with filtered templates. See Table 2. The best results were with a -40 dB noise floor, resulting in a 46% recognition rate. This is somewhat surprising, in that this generates a larger dynamic range than is usually recommended for LPC analysis.

Table 2: Summary of Recognition Rates

	Recognition Rate
Itakura's original score (1)	40%
Symmetric Itakura score (2)	46%
Selective LPC	29%
LPC with smooth noise floor	45%
Smooth noise floor and 6000 Hz bandwidth	44%
Average LPC, -50 dB noise floor	43%
Average LPC, -40 dB noise floor	46%
Average LPC, -30 dB noise floor	44%
Average LPC, -20 dB noise floor	42%
Average LPC using full band templates (-50 dB)	45%

SUMMARY

In this paper, a symmetric version of Itakura's spectral match score is shown to be more effective than his original score in locating and identifying target words. This paper goes on to describe a series of experiments which demonstrate that oversampling a speech signal encodes important energy information in the in-band to out-of-band energy ratio. This information is effectively used by a symmetric variation of Itakura's spectral match score. However, variations in the out-of-band noise floor can cause difficulties. The described average LPC technique alleviates these difficulties, and makes effective use of this information without the need to actually change the sampling rate.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Itakura, "Minimum Prediction Residual Principle Applied to Speech Recognition", IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, Vol. 23, No. 1, pp. 67-72, February 1975.
- [2] R. W. Christiansen and C. K. Rushforth, "Detecting and Locating Key Words in Continuous Speech Using Linear Predictive Coding", IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, Vol. 25, pp. 361-367, October 1977.
- [3] L. R. Rabiner and C. E. Schmidt, "Application of Dynamic Time Warping to Connected Digit Recognition", IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, Vol. 28, No. 4, pp. 377-388, August 1980.
- [4] T. G. Stockham, and others, "Blind Deconvolution Through Digital Signal Processing", Proceedings of the IEEE, Vol. 63, No. 4, pp. 678-692, April 1975.
- [5] H. Sakoe and S. Chiba, "Dynamic Programming Algorithm Optimization for Spoken Word Recognition", IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, Vol. 26, No. 1, pp. 43-49, February 1978.
- [6] D.J. Goodman, and others, "Objective and Subjective Performance of Tandem Connections of Waveform Coders with an LPC Vocoder", The Bell System Technical Journal, Vol. 58, No. 3, pp. 601-629, March 1979.
- [7] J. D. Markel and A. H. Gray, Linear Prediction of Speech, pp. 146-151, Springer-Verlag, 1979.